

HUMOUR IN THE UPBRINGING AND EDUCATION OF THE MODERN TEENAGER

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Abstract. *The article is about humour and the role of it in the education and upbringing of modern teenagers. As we know, humour and its natural expression - laughter - has an undeniable pedagogical value as one of the new technologies. The use of this medium can become a reference point for improving the effectiveness of the process of upbringing, education and personal development.*

Key words: *humour, laughter, education, upbringing, teenagers, problems in education, pedagogy and psychology.*

ЮМОР В ВОСПИТАНИИ И ОБРАЗОВАНОСТИ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ПОДРОСТКА

Аннотация. *Статья посвящена юмору и его роли в образовании и воспитании современных подростков. Как мы знаем, юмор и его естественное выражение - смех - имеет неоспоримую педагогическую ценность как одна из новых технологий. Использование этой среды может стать ориентиром для повышения эффективности процесса воспитания, образования и личностного развития.*

Ключевые слова: *юмор, смех, образование, воспитание, подростки, проблемы в образовании, педагогика и психология.*

Modern education is one of the means of solving the most important problems not only for society but also for individuals. In any state, the nature of the education system is determined by the socioeconomic and political system, as well as by the cultural, historical and national characteristics of the country. One of the most important principles of state education policy is to improve the efficiency of the pedagogical process. Modern Russian society requires a well-rounded individual capable of critical thinking, independent decision-making and creative approach to any matter. Humour and its natural expression - laughter - has an undeniable pedagogical value as one of the new technologies.

The use of this medium can become a reference point for improving the effectiveness of the process of upbringing, education and personal development. In the history of pedagogy scientists have always emphasized the importance of humor in education and upbringing. Foreign and domestic philosophers, sociologists, psychologists and educators (M. F. Quintilian, Y. B. Borev, O. A. Krivtsun, A. Bergson, V.Ya. Propp, S.L. Rubinstein, L.S. Vygotsky, V.A. Sukhomlinsky, A.N. Luk, B.Z. Vulfov, V.D. Ivanov, V.S. Kukushin, N.N. Nikitina, S.D. Yakusheva, etc.). However, the problem of the importance of humor as an educational tool has not yet been sufficiently developed in pedagogy and psychology. There are a number of contradictions, overcoming of which will contribute to improving the effectiveness of upbringing and education of adolescents by means of humor.

These are contradictions between:

-The society's need in a new type of psycho-pedagogical specialists, capable of using humor in pedagogical activity and insufficient development of this problem in pedagogical science;

-the need for the use of humour in pedagogical practice, in the system of professional education and the lack of adequate training of teachers to solve this problem;

-the possibility of humor in the development of associative thinking and outlook of teenagers in the educational process and insufficient actualization of the humorous component of the content of the educational process.

These contradictions determined the topic of our work, the aim of which is humour in upbringing and education of a modern teenager. It is difficult to overestimate the importance of humour in human communication. People's understanding of each other, their cooperation, the joint process of creation and organization of communication at different levels largely depend on how humor is used by the participants of communication. The role of humour for a man is enormous. For him it is one of the most important professional qualities and a means of acting. The mastery of humour is, above all, the ability to improvise, to maintain a friendly classroom atmosphere and an interest in the subject.

A teacher who skilfully uses various means of humour (puns, proverbs, sayings, historical anecdotes, travesties, burlesques, metaphors, hyperbole, etc.), thereby reducing tension in the classroom, refreshing attention, developing associative thinking in the audience, broadening their horizons and having an emotional impact on the audience. So what is humour? One of the simplest and most precise definitions belongs to V.I. Dahl: "Humour is a cheerful, sharp, humorous fold of mind, able to notice and sharply expose strangeness of customs, orders and manners". Although humour is broader than any definition, he pointed out its essential feature: it is a property of the human psyche consisting in the ability to "spot the strangeness" [5, p. 730]. Many events of the surrounding world are perceived as natural, logical, and correct.

The ability to detect strangeness in one's environment helps one to orient in the world, increases one's adaptability to life in society. As man has an inherent capacity for self-reflection, he is happy to know that he is able to detect errors and absurdities. This creates one of the prerequisites for the formation of sense of humour - taste, desire, orientation (installation) to find absurd and funny in everyday environment [13, p. 55]. A. Quintilian said that learning should be joyful. One of the leading Russian teachers V. A. Sukhomlinsky was a supporter of creating school of joy. He is the key figure in defining the problem of humour in education.

He gave an important role in education to the teacher's word, artistic style of presentation, composing together with children small stories and fairy tales, imbued with upbeat humor. V.A. Sukhomlinsky regarded humour as a powerful A. Sukhomlinsky regarded humour as a powerful means of influence. He argued that the ability to see in the breach of discipline funny and shame funny - this is the ability to penetrate the mind and heart of the spiritual world of the child: "The child can not live without laughter.

When children laugh, one should not get angry, unnecessary and inappropriate laughter should be shamed with humour, i.e. with laughter" [11, p. 355]. The ability to laugh is a genuinely human trait; sensitivity to laughter, an inner "readiness" to laugh requires great development, vigorous activity, a play of mental powers. Laughter is the flip side of thinking. To develop in the

child the ability to laugh, to affirm a sense of humor means to strengthen his mental strength and abilities, to teach to think subtly and to see the world wisely [11, p. 348].

A teacher should not lose his or her sense of humour when dealing with children's pranks. One should try to see oneself reflexively in the context of today's situation of pranks, maybe even more serious manifestations of indiscipline or slovenliness. A sense of humour is a necessary quality for a teacher [3, p. 511].

The presence or absence of sense of humour can be judged by the way a person understands jokes, jokes, cartoons, caricatures, whether he/she can perceive the comicality of a situation, whether he/she can laugh not only at others, but also when he/she becomes the object of a joke. Absence or insufficient expression of sense of humour can indicate both a reduced emotional level and insufficient intellectual development [10, p. 875].

Conclusion. It is not uncommon at conferences and conventions for participants to begin a serious report with a funny parable. This invariably helps to win the benevolent attention of an audience not only with the force of arguments, but also with a sparkling humor, which helps to depreciate all cunning arguments of opponents without spending any time or effort on them. What matters here, therefore, is the ability to transcend the usual boundaries that constrain thought; this ability is not limited to science alone.

It is rather a characteristic of the individual and not just a peculiarity of thinking [7, p. 137]. Thus, the upbringing and education of adolescents is one of the most pressing problems of modern society. Education is seen primarily as a process of personal development and self-development, connected with mastering the socially significant experience of mankind, embodied in knowledge, change, creative activity and emotional-valuable attitude to the world, constituting the sphere of feelings and emotions.

This is what fills the life of a teenager with special awe, enriches his spiritual world, allows him to perceive the environment through the prism of his experiences, to enjoy and rejoice, to grieve and suffer, i.e. to live a full life. For humor and laughter is the flip side of thinking. To develop a child's ability to laugh, to affirm a sense of humour, is to strengthen his mental strength and capacity, to teach him to think subtly and to see the world wisely.

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